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P. M. B. 1515,
ILORIN, NIGERIA**
geostudiesjournal@gmail.com

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Address:	Department of Geography & Environmental Management, Faculty of Social Science, University of Ilorin, Nigeria.
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SOCIO-ECONOMIC STATUS OF FREIGHT FORWARDERS AS DETERMINANTS OF COMPLIANCE WITH TRADE FACILITATION POLICIES IN NIGERIA

Ademola Benson Irinyemi and Adeyinka Peter Ajayi

Department of Transport Management

Redeemer's University, Ede.

Corresponding author's E-mail: ajayia@run.edu.ng

Abstract: *This research analysed the confluence between Social Economic Situation (SES) and the willingness to comply with Trade Facilitation (CTF) policies among freight forwarders in the Lagos Port Complex. Evidence from across different climes shows that the CTF has incentivised national economic development. The research employed the positivist methodological approach. The multistage and simple random sampling techniques were employed to gather data from 392 professional freight forwarders, who provided the desired information relating to the study's objectives. A Multiple Regression Analysis (MRA) was used in predicting the existence of relationships among the dependent and independent variables. The results from the MRA established the likelihood of a causal relationship between the dependent variable, CTF, and the independent explanatory SES variables (Gender, Age, Marital Status, Educational Status, and Financial Capability). The MRA indicated that gender significantly predicted the commitment to governmental policies that encourages trade facilitation ($\beta = -.21$, $t = -4.28$, $p < .05$), ditto for age ($\beta = .20$, $t = 3.90$, $p < .05$), and education ($\beta = .17$, $t = 3.34$, $p < .05$). Also, the result from the One-way Analysis of Variance indicated that Marital Status significantly influenced CTF [$F(4, 387) = 4.469$, $p < .05$]. The study recommends developing strategies to enhance targeted SES factors (such as literacy, gender, age, and marital status) in recruitment and staff capacity development to strengthen sector engagement in the government's drive for trade facilitation.*

Keywords: Social Economic Situation, Compliance to Trade Facilitation, Freight Forwarders, Governmental Policies, Economic Development.

INTRODUCTION

Trade facilitation policies are crucial for promoting efficient and seamless international trade by simplifying customs procedures, reducing trade barriers, and enhancing transparency in cross-border transactions (Vu & Tang, 2022; Ajayi, 2020). These policies aim to streamline trade processes, reduce costs, and improve the overall trade environment. Efficient trade facilitation policies are crucial for developing countries like Nigeria, where international trade is vital to economic growth and development (Sakyi & Afesorgbor, 2019; Ajayi, 2023).

Nigeria is a vibrant player in international trade, with significant volumes of imports and exports passing through its borders (Shahriar & Abdullahi, 2023; Oni & Ajayi, 2025). Nigeria's 2024 record of USD 89.9 billion was the third-highest total merchandise trade volume in Africa (Africa Import Export Bank, 2025). Despite the trade sector's seemingly high performance in the country, the prevailing view among key stakeholders is that it is still grossly underperforming. Some undeniable tell-tale signs that lend credence to this assertion include the country's inability to annex its potentials optimally as a strategic partner in Economic Community of West Africa States (ECOWAS), The African

Continental Free Trade Area (AfCTA), and the United States of America owned Africa Growth Opportunity Act (AGOA) initiatives (Oni and Ajayi, 2025; Nwachukwu, 2025; Olujobi, 2026; Ajayi, 2026).

A salient contributor to Nigeria's unenviable international performance is the country's freight forwarding industry (Ajayi, 2021; Fagbo-Lawal et al., 2023). Freight forwarding optimizes international trade competitiveness by transforming logistics from a cost center into a strategic advantage. Freight Forwarders act as intermediaries between shippers and global transport networks, allowing businesses to reach new markets efficiently, speeding up customs clearance processes, enhancing end-to-end visibility of goods-in-transit through the latest technologies (Elliott & Bonsignori, 2019), and reliably addressing numerous trade facilitation challenges.

Some of the peculiar challenges of freight forwarding business practices in Nigeria include cumbersome customs procedures, bureaucratic delays, inadequate infrastructure, a lack of professionalism among industrial participants, and a parlous state of institutional control (Oni & Ajayi, 2025). Experts affirmed that these factors hinder the smooth flow of goods across borders, resulting in increased costs and inhibited the competitiveness of Nigerian trading despite the availability of bilateral commercial initiatives like the Economic Community of West Africa States (ECOWAS) at the sub-regional level, The African Continental Free Trade Area (AfCFTA) at the regional/continental level, and the African Growth Opportunity Act (AGOA) at the global level (Osabohien, et al, 2021; Central Bank of Nigeria, 2024; Olujobi, 2026). For example, the annexation of the latent benefits in AfCFTA is critical for Nigeria, as it creates an inroad into a massive, integrated market of over 54 countries, valued

at over USD2.5 trillion (Africa Import and Export Bank, 2025).

Socioeconomic status (SES) refers to an individual's social and economic position within society, influenced by factors such as income level, education, and occupation (Ajayi, 2012; Manstead, 2018; Ajayi, 2020). SES has significantly impacted individuals' behaviour, decision-making, and policy adoption across various domains. While there is scant evidence on the nexus between SES and the willingness to adopt trade facilitation policies in the maritime sector, literature search indicated that individuals' SES often shaped their access to resources, knowledge, and their willingness to conform to operational standards (Pham-Truffert et al., 2020; Ajayi and Mazinyo, 2020).

Despite the recognized importance of SES as a catalyst in shaping policy adoption (Tucho, 2021; Ajayi, 2021; Ajayi, 2023; Tartaglia et al., 2025), empirical research has yet to examine its specific impact on commitment to trade facilitation policies among Nigerian freight forwarders. This research bridged this lacuna by investigating the link between socioeconomic status and policy commitment among Nigerian freight forwarders. The main objective was to examine how socioeconomic factors influence Nigerian freight forwarders' commitment to trade facilitation policies and to unravel the impact of these factors on achieving a positive trade balance in the country.

This study holds significance for several stakeholders involved in trade facilitation in Nigeria. Firstly, policymakers can benefit from a deeper understanding of the relationship between socioeconomic status and policy commitment. Such insights can inform the design of targeted policies and interventions to enhance the adoption of trade

facilitation measures among freight forwarders. Secondly, Nigerian freight forwarders can gain awareness of the role of their socioeconomic status in their commitment to trade facilitation policies, enabling them to make informed decisions and take proactive measures to align their practices with policy objectives. Lastly, the study contributes to the existing literature by addressing the research gap in the link between socioeconomic status and commitment to trade facilitation policies in the context of Nigerian freight forwarders. This research can serve as a foundation for future studies and provide valuable insights for other developing countries facing similar trade facilitation challenges.

This paper is structured into five sections. The introductory section provides background and highlights the study's motivation. The second section reviewed the extant literature on the interaction between trade facilitation and international trade and explored the relationship between maritime transportation and economic growth. Section three highlighted the methodology. Section four discussed the results and findings. Finally, the study concludes in section five and offers practical recommendations.

LITERATURE REVIEW

OVERVIEW OF TRADE FACILITATION POLICIES AND THEIR IMPACT ON INTERNATIONAL TRADE

Trade facilitation policies play a crucial role in promoting international trade by reducing transaction costs, improving efficiency, and enhancing the overall competitiveness of nations in the global market (Engman, 2005; Wassie et al, 2025) These policies encompass a wide range of measures to simplify and harmonise trade procedures, streamline

customs processes, enhance logistics and infrastructure, and promote information exchange between trading partners (Peterson, 2017; Wassie et al, 2025). Implementing effective trade facilitation policies has been shown to have significant positive effects on trade flows and economic growth. For instance, studies have found that improvements in customs procedures, such as the simplification and automation of documentation requirements, lead to a reduction in trade costs and an increase in trade volumes (Chimilila et al., 2014; Lan and Yeu, 2013; Elliott & Bonsignori, 2019; Moisé & Le Bris, 2013). These findings highlight the importance of efficient customs processes in facilitating trade and fostering economic development.

Investments in infrastructure and logistics also facilitate trade. Serebrisky et. al. (2016) conducted a study examining the impact of port efficiency on trade flows in Latin America and found that improvements in port infrastructure and operations positively influenced trade volumes. Similarly, Meranda et al (2026) explored the relationship between transportation infrastructure and trade costs and found that better transportation infrastructure leads to lower trade costs and higher trade volumes.

In addition to reducing trade costs and improving logistics, trade facilitation policies enhance market access and attract foreign direct investment (FDI). Hassan (2020) highlights that effective trade facilitation measures create a favourable business environment by reducing administrative burdens and enhancing transparency, thereby attracting FDI and fostering economic growth. Moreover, these policies facilitate the participation of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in international trade, enabling them to overcome resource

constraints and compete effectively in the global market (Lwesya, 2021).

Furthermore, trade facilitation policies play a crucial role in promoting regional integration and enabling participation in global value chains (Wassie et al, 2025; Africa Import and Export Bank, 2025). Nguenkwe & Tchitchoua (2019) examined the impact of trade facilitation on regional trade integration and found that improvements in trade facilitation measures led to a significant increase in intra-regional trade. Meranda et al., (2026). investigated the role of trade facilitation and contemporary port infrastructure in global value chains and found that efficient trade facilitation practices positively influenced a country's participation in global value chains, thereby increasing exports and economic development.

In summary, trade facilitation policies have a profound impact on international trade by reducing trade costs, enhancing logistics and infrastructure, facilitating market access, attracting FDI, promoting regional integration, and enabling participation in global value chains. These policies are vital for countries seeking to enhance their competitiveness and realise the full potential of international trade. The literature provides robust evidence of a positive relationship between trade facilitation policies and trade flows, underscoring the need for effective policy implementation to foster economic growth and development.

SOCIOECONOMIC STATUS AND ITS RELEVANCE TO POLICY COMMITMENT

Socioeconomic status (SES) is a multidimensional concept that encompasses an individual's or a group's economic and social position in society, including factors

such as income, education, occupation, and wealth (Fitzpatrick et al., 2015). SES has been recognized as a significant determinant of various social and behavioural outcomes, including attitudes and behaviour related to policy commitment.

The relevance of SES to policy commitment is evident in the literature across different domains. In the context of public health, studies have shown that individuals with higher SES are more likely to engage in health-promoting behaviours, such as adopting healthy diets, engaging in physical activity, and adhering to medical treatments (Byerly et al., 2018). This can be attributed to the greater access to resources, information, and social networks that individuals with higher SES typically possess, enabling them to make informed decisions and take actions that align with policy goals (Ajayi and Mazinyo, 2020; Tucho, 2022; Tartaglia et al, 2025).

In education, SES has been found to influence parents' commitment to educational policies and their involvement in their children's education. Research suggests that parents with higher SES tend to be more engaged in their children's schooling, including participation in parent-teacher associations, volunteering, and providing academic support at home (Benner et al., 2016). These findings highlight the role of SES in shaping parents' commitment to educational policies and their ability to actively contribute to their implementation.

Furthermore, studies have examined the relationship between SES and political participation, indicating that individuals with higher SES are more likely to engage in political activities and demonstrate higher levels of civic commitment (Kahne et al., 2012). This can be attributed to the greater access to education, resources, and networks that individuals with higher SES typically

have, enabling them to navigate political processes, stay informed about policy issues, and participate in decision-making processes.

In the specific context of policy commitment related to trade facilitation, the influence of SES has received limited attention in the literature. However, it is reasonable to hypothesize that SES may influence stakeholders' commitment to trade facilitation policies. For instance, freight forwarders, as intermediaries in international trade, may vary in their commitment to trade facilitation policies based on their socioeconomic characteristics. Those with higher SES may have better access to information, resources, and networks, enabling them to engage in policy implementation and advocacy more effectively.

By exploring the link between SES and commitment to trade facilitation policies among Nigerian freight forwarders, this study aims to contribute to the understanding of how socioeconomic factors shape stakeholders' engagement in policy processes. The findings of this research can provide insights into the factors that influence policy commitment and inform strategies to enhance stakeholder engagement and effectiveness in trade facilitation initiatives.

PREVIOUS STUDIES ON THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN SOCIOECONOMIC STATUS AND POLICY COMMITMENT

Research exploring the relationship between socioeconomic status (SES) and policy commitment has provided valuable insights across various domains. These studies have shed light on the influence of SES on individuals' attitudes, behaviours, and engagement in policy-related activities.

In environmental policy, several studies have examined the role of SES in shaping individuals' commitment to environmental protection and sustainable behaviours. For instance, Ballew et. al. (2020) found that individuals with higher SES tend to have more favourable attitudes towards environmental policies and are more likely to engage in pro-environmental behaviours. Similarly, Delclòs-Alió et al. (2022) reported that higher-SES individuals are more supportive of policies aimed at addressing environmental issues. These studies indicate that individuals with higher SES may have greater resources and awareness, which contribute to their greater commitment to environmental policies.

In the context of social policies, research has explored the relationship between SES and commitment to policies addressing issues such as poverty alleviation and social welfare. Studies have shown that individuals with higher SES are more likely to support policies aimed at reducing income inequality, providing social safety nets, and improving access to education and healthcare (Graham, 2010; Wahlbeck & McDaid, 2012). This suggests that SES influences individuals' commitment to policies aimed at addressing social disparities and promoting equal opportunities.

Furthermore, studies have examined the relationship between SES and commitment to policies related to labour markets and employment. For example, Landsbergis et. al. (2014) found that individuals with higher SES are more likely to support policies that promote job security and workplace protections. Similarly, research on welfare policies has shown that individuals with higher SES support policies that encourage work requirements and personal responsibility (O'Neill, 2013; Schmidt & Hoffman, 2018). These findings suggest that SES influences individuals' attitudes and support for policies

that impact employment and labour market dynamics.

Although limited research specifically examines the relationship between SES and commitment to trade facilitation policies, these previous studies provide a foundation for understanding how SES may influence policy commitment. The findings suggest that SES can shape individuals' attitudes, behaviours, and support for policies across various domains. Considering this, it is reasonable to hypothesize that SES may also influence stakeholders' commitment to trade facilitation policies.

By exploring the link between SES and commitment to trade facilitation policies among Nigerian freight forwarders, this study aims to contribute to the literature by examining how socioeconomic factors influence stakeholders' engagement and commitment in international trade. The findings will provide valuable insights into the relationship between SES and policy commitment, specifically in the trade facilitation domain, and contribute to a more comprehensive understanding of the factors shaping stakeholders' engagement in policy processes.

THEORETICAL PERSPECTIVES ON SOCIOECONOMIC STATUS AND POLICY COMMITMENT

Understanding the relationship between socioeconomic status (SES) and policy commitment requires drawing on relevant theoretical perspectives that illuminate how SES influences individuals' attitudes, behaviours, and engagement in policy-related activities.

One theoretical perspective that sheds light on this relationship is the social capital theory. According to social capital theory (Putnam,

2000), individuals with higher SES tend to have greater access to social networks, resources, and information, which enable them to engage in policy-related activities and exhibit higher levels of commitment. Higher-SES individuals are more likely to have connections to influential individuals or organizations, enabling them to gather information, advocate for policy change, and participate in decision-making processes (Adler & Newman, 2002). Social capital theory suggests that SES influences policy commitment by facilitating access to networks and resources that enhance individuals' engagement and efficacy in policy-related endeavours.

Another relevant theoretical perspective is the human capital theory. Human capital theory posits that individuals' skills, knowledge, and educational attainment, often correlated with SES, contribute to their ability to engage in policy processes and demonstrate commitment (Ladd, 2012). Individuals with higher education and skills, typically associated with higher SES, may possess more excellent policy-related knowledge, analytical abilities, and critical thinking skills. These attributes can enhance individuals' understanding of policy issues, facilitate active participation in policy-related activities, and increase their commitment to policy goals (Bourdieu, 1986). Human capital theory suggests that SES influences policy commitment by enabling individuals to acquire the skills and knowledge needed to engage meaningfully with policy matters.

Additionally, the equity theory provides insights into the relationship between SES and policy commitment. According to equity theory (Adams, 1965), individuals evaluate fairness and equity in the distribution of resources and benefits within a social context. SES, as an indicator of one's relative position in society, shapes individuals' perceptions of

fairness and the extent to which they feel included and represented in policy processes. Individuals with higher SES may perceive themselves as having a stake in policy outcomes and may be more committed to policies that align with their interests and values. On the other hand, individuals with lower SES may perceive policies as unjust or biased, leading to lower levels of commitment (Pickett & Wilkinson, 2015). Equity theory highlights how SES influences policy commitment through individuals' perceptions of fairness and their sense of inclusion in policy processes.

These theoretical perspectives and literature review provided a foundation for understanding the relationship between SES and policy commitment. Social capital theory emphasises the role of networks and resources, human capital theory highlights the influence of education and skills, and equity theory examines individuals' perceptions of fairness. By integrating these theoretical perspectives, this study seeks to explore how SES influences Nigerian freight forwarders' commitment to trade facilitation policies, accounting for the multidimensional nature of SES and its potential mechanisms of influence.

This extensive literature and theoretical review provided a basis for the derivation of the hypothesis that succinctly captured the main objective of this study, and it is stated thus:

Hypothesis: The Socioeconomic situation (SES) of the sampled freight forwarder does not significantly influence their commitment to governmental policies that encourage trade facilitation in Nigeria.

RESEARCH METHODS

A positivist research approach was employed to investigate the link between socioeconomic status (SES) and commitment to trade facilitation policies among Nigerian freight forwarders. The research protocol was approved by the ethical committee of Redeemer's University (Nigeria). As per the dictates of the ethical approval obtained, all respondents who participated in the study were duly notified of the research's aim. Then, informed consent was obtained from the participants. As part of the ethical approval, there is assurance of confidentiality for all participants in the study. All sourced data were documented by code, rather than the respondent's name. A survey was conducted among practicing Nigerian freight forwarders to collect the necessary data. The fieldwork was conducted at the Apapa Seaport, where all the national freight forwarder associations have their headquarters. The national offices also maintain registers containing the details of all registered members. The study population participating in the study is freight forwarders in Nigeria, while the sample frame is drawn from the registers of various associations (Table 1).

SCALE DEVELOPMENT

While pockets of studies has examined the nexus between the SES of workers in the transport sector and their attitudinal dispositions to key factors impacting industrial practices like crime incidences and insecurity on transport routes (Ajayi, 2010; Carpentier, 2014; Ajayi and Ajayi, 2014; Ajayi, 2016; Lavrinc, 2016; Paul, 2018) safety (Ajayi, 2020; Lawal-Fagbo et al, 2023), impacts on the use of psychoactive substances on operational performances (Ajayi and Mazinyo, 2020), there are scanty pieces of evidence of studies which investigated the linkage between SES and the

willingness to comply with trade facilitation policies among freight forwarders in the Nigerian milieu.

For scientific measurement of the variables, a Likert-like scale was used. As previously stated, some variables, such as the impact of SES on compliance with the Standard Operating Procedure (SOP) guiding safety practices in the transport industry, have scales that were developed and used in earlier research (Ajayi and Mazinyo, 2020; Lawal-Fagbo et al., 2023; Tartaglia et al., 2025). These scales were adapted to reflect the interaction between SES and 'commitment to governmental policies'. On the other hand, new operational definitions for measuring items were developed to evaluate variables that had not been previously used in prior research. To this end, a measurable operational definition was provided for a construct like 'commitment to governmental

policies impact trade facilitation'. A pre-field exercise helped ensure the validity and reliability of the research instruments.

Additionally, Cronbach's alpha was computed for each constructed multi-item instruments to assess their internal reliability and effectiveness in measuring the research variables. The rule of thumb is that a Cronbach's alpha lower than 0.60 means poor reliability, values between 0.6 and 0.7 are acceptable, and values equal to or higher than 0.70 indicate good scale reliability (Churchill, 1979; Simich-Levi et al, 2003; Quesada et al, 2012; Ajayi, 2016; Ajayi, 2026). The interaction between SES and commitment to government policies subscale which consisted of 10 items have a Cronbach's alpha of .80 ($\alpha=.80$), trade facilitation subscale with 8 items .79 ($\alpha=.79$), and impact of commitment to policies on trade facilitation with 9 items .81 ($\alpha=.81$). Both descriptive and inferential statistics are thereafter used to analyse the data and to test the derived hypothesis.

Table 1: Population and the Derivation of Sample Size for Study

S/N	Name of Association	Numbers of Registered Members Available	Proposed Sampled	10% Percentage %
1	ANCLA	1204	120.4	10%
2	NAGAFF	1005	100.5	10%
3	AREFN	554	55.4	10%
4	APFLON	657	65.7	10%
5	NAFFAC	304	30.4	10%
6	NCFLD	356	35.6	10%
		4070	408	

Source: Field Survey, 2026

Records from the six nationally registered freight forwarder associations in Nigeria served as the sampling frames for the study. The six nationally registered freight forwarding associations, as listed by the Council for Registered Freight Forwarding in

Nigeria (CRFFN), are the regulatory body responsible for freight forwarding businesses in Nigeria. are: Association of Nigeria Licensed Customs Agents (ANLCA), The National Association of Government Approved Freight Forwarders (NAGAFF),

Association of Registered Freight Forwarders, Nigeria (AREFN), The African Association of Professional Freight Forwarders and Logistics of Nigeria (APFLON), The National Association of Freight Forwarders and Consolidators (NAFFAC), and The National Council for Freight and Logistics Directors (NCFLD). The record indicated that 4070 members were registered with the association during the study period (Table 1). The study was done between March and September 2025.

A double-stage sampling technique was used to select the participants in the research. At the first stage, the targeted population that actually participated in the study was chosen. To obtain an objective sampling of the targeted population, 10% of the sampling frame (408) was selected, in line with established guidelines for estimating sample size in research on social and management sciences (Martínez-Mesa et al., 2014; Ajayi, 2026). At the second stage, the registers for each association were consulted, and every tenth (10th) numbered/listed members were selected for the study. Each association's headquarters was visited, and questionnaires were administered to the selected participants. For respondents who were unavailable, the questionnaires were mailed. Out of the 408 respondents that were sampled, 392 (96.3%) questionnaires were retrieved.

The survey data were analysed using statistical techniques, including regression analysis, to test the developed hypothesis. Regression analysis helped assess the relationship between SES and commitment to trade facilitation policies while controlling for potential confounding factors. Mediation and moderation analyses were also employed to examine the mediating role of policy attitudes and the moderating role of institutional factors.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

RESULTS

This section presents the results of the analysis. A structured questionnaire was used to collect information on SES indicators, policy attitudes, and commitment to trade facilitation policies. Descriptive statistics were used to highlight the relevance of these factors in understanding the sample. Measures such as mean, standard deviation, and frequency distributions were used to summarize the data. The SES indicators, including income, education level, occupation, and asset ownership, were analyzed to understand the participants' distribution and variation in socioeconomic status.

Table 1: Frequency Distribution showing the Social Related Factors

Factors	Options	Frequency	%
Gender	Male	335	85.5
	Female	57	14.5
	Total	392	100.0
Age	21 years - 30 years	27	6.9
	31 years - 40 years	55	14.0
	41 years - 50 years	153	39.0
	51 years - 60 years	131	33.4
	61 years - 65 years	26	6.6
	Total	392	100.0
Marital Status	Single	53	13.5
	Married	230	58.7
	Separated	36	9.2
	Divorced	53	13.5
	Widowed	20	5.1
	Total	392	100.0
Educational Qualification	SSCE	52	13.3
	ND/NCE	27	6.9
	First Degree/ HND	214	54.6
	PGD/MBA/MSc/MA	99	25.3
	Total	392	100.0
How long have you been in the practice of freight forwarding?	1 year - 5 years	45	11.5
	6 years - 10 years	77	19.6
	11 years - 15 years	179	45.7
	16 years - 20 years	44	11.2
	21 years & above	47	12.0
	Total	392	100.0
Financial Capability	₦500,000 - ₦5,000,000	97	24.7
	₦5,000,000 - ₦10,000,000	129	32.9
	₦10,000,000 - ₦15,000,000	166	42.3
	Total	392	100.0

Source: Author's field report, 2026

The social demographics of the sampled respondents revealed that the majority were male; however, both genders were duly represented. This was such that 85.5% of the respondents were males, while 14.5% were females. The age categorisation of the respondents indicated that 6.9% were between the ages of 21 and 30 years, 14% were between the ages of 31 and 40 years, 39% were between the ages of 41 and 50 years, 33.4% were between 51 and 60 years, while

6.6% were between 61 and 65 years of age. It was noted that 13.5% of respondents were single, 58.7% were married, 9.2% were separated, 13.5% were divorced, and 5.1% were widowed. Regarding educational attainment, 13.3% had a secondary school leaving certificate (SSCE), 6.9% had either a National Diploma or a Nigeria Certificate of Education, and 54.6% had either a Higher National Diploma or a Bachelor's degree. In comparison, 25.3% had a postgraduate degree.

On the economic aspect, the test on the duration of the respondents' practice of freight forwarding revealed that 11.5% had practiced it for years ranging between 1 and 5 years, 19.6% had practice it for between 6 and 10 years, 45.7% had practice it for between 11 and 15 years, 11.2% had practice it for between 16 and 20 years, while those that had practice it for over 20 years were 12%. Lastly, the respondents' financial capabilities were observed. It was noted that 24.7% of the respondents earn between ₦500,000 and ₦5,000,000 annually, 32.9% earn between ₦5,000,000 and ₦10,000,000, while 42.3% earn between ₦10,000,000 - ₦15,000,000. This revealed that the sampled participants were representative of the various categories of individuals within the study population, thereby limiting any of bias in the study outcome that could emanate from such demographic variations.

To test the derived hypothesis, a regression model is formulated. The regression model depicts and assesses the relationship between a dependent variable and one or more independent variables (Churchill, 1979: Akbulaev and Bayramli,2020: Ajayi., 2020: Ajayi, 2023). Y represents the dependent variable, which is also known as the outcome or variable you are trying to predict or explain using the other variables in the model. X on

the other hand, represents the independent variables (also called predictor or explanatory variables), which are used to explain or predict Y (Churchill, 1979: Akbulaev and Bayramli,2020: Ajayi, 2020: Ajayi, 2023). The general regression model is depicted thus:

$$Y = a + b_0 + b_1X_1 + b_2X_2 + \dots + b_pX_p + e \dots \dots \dots$$

For the purpose of this study, the three derived hypotheses are:

$$CTF = a + b_0 + b_1SESG + b_2SESA + b_3SESE + b_4SESW + b_5SESF + e \dots \dots \dots (i)$$

Where:

b₀ intersection, b₁, and b₂ = regression coefficients, and e = regression error

CTF: Compliance to Trade Facilitation (Dependent Variable)

SESG: Socioeconomic Situation Gender (Independent Variable)

SESA: Socioeconomic Situation Age (Independent Variable)

SESE: Socioeconomic Situation Education (Independent Variable)

SESW: Socioeconomic Situation Work Experience (Independent Variable)

SESF: Socioeconomic Situation Finance (Independent Variable).

Table 2: Multiple Regression showing the Prediction of Commitment to Policies Encouraging Trade Facilitation by Socioeconomic Situations

Predictors	β	t	p	R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	df	F
				.37	.14	.13	5, 386	12.44**
Gender	-.21	-4.28**	< .05					
Age	.20	3.90**	< .05					
Educational Qualification	.17	3.34**	< .05					
Work Experience	-.05	-.97	> .05					
Financial Capability	.07	1.37	> .05					

Note: ** p < 0.01, * p < 0.05, N= 392.

Source: Authors' Analysis, 2026

The findings in Table 2 indicated that gender significantly predicted the commitment to governmental policies that encourage trade facilitation ($\beta = -.21$, $t = -4.28$, $p < .05$). Based on the dichotomous nature of gender and how it's been coded as male-1, female-2, the result revealed that males had higher commitment to policies encouraging trade facilitation compared to their female counterparts. It was also noted that age had significant influence on commitment to governmental policies that encourages trade facilitation ($\beta = .20$, $t = 3.90$, $p < .05$). It was also noted that age had a significant influence on commitment to governmental policies that encourage trade facilitation ($\beta = .20$, $t = 3.90$, $p < .05$). This implied that the older freight forwarders were, the greater their commitment to governmental policies that encourage trade facilitation. The result revealed that educational qualification significantly predicted commitment to governmental policies that encourage trade facilitation ($\beta = .17$, $t = 3.34$, $p < .05$). By implication commitment increases with increasing educational attainment. The

influence of years of work experience on commitment was not significant ($\beta = -.05$, $t = -.97$, $p > .05$). Also financial capability was not a significant predictor of commitment to governmental policies that encourages trade facilitation ($\beta = .07$, $t = 1.37$, $p > .05$).

Jointly, the identified socioeconomic factors significantly influenced commitment to governmental policies that encourage trade facilitation thereby contributing a significant 13% to the total variance observed in commitment [Adjusted R² = .13, F(5, 386) = 12.44, $p < .05$].

Some of the variables considered as socioeconomic were measured in scales that could not be considered in the regression analysis (nominal scale) and they were not dichotomous, thus they were tested using applicable tools independently on commitment to governmental policies that encourages trade facilitation. One such factor is marital status and it was tested using One-way ANOVA.

Table 3. One-Way ANOVA showing the influence of Marital Status on Commitment to Government Policies that Encourage Trade Facilitation

Source	SS	df	MS	F	p
Between Groups	132.652	4	33.163	4.469	< .05
Within Groups	2871.542	387	7.420		
Total	3004.194	391			

Source: Authors' Analysis, 2026

Table 3 indicated that marital status had a significant influence on commitment to governmental policies that encourages trade facilitation [F (4, 387) = 4.469, p < .05]. This implied that the marital status of freight forwarders reflect differently on their commitment to governmental policies that

encourages trade facilitation. In order to have a better understanding of the category of marital status that is most influential and also identify the mean differences that led to the observed significant outcome, descriptive and scheffe post hoc test was conducted and presented in table.

Table 4: Scheffe Post-hoc Test showing the Mean Differences in groupings of Marital Status on Commitment to Government Policies that Encourage Trade Facilitation

Marital Status	N	Mean	SD	1	2	3	4	5
1. Single	53	18.15	3.41	-				
2. Separated	230	19.34	2.90	1.19	-			
3. Married	36	20.39	1.76	2.24*	1.05	-		
4. Divorced	53	19.91	1.42	1.76*	.56	.48	-	
5. Widowed	20	19.10	2.53	.95	.24	1.29	.81	-
Total	392	19.34	2.77					

Source: Authors' Analysis, 2026

Table 4 presents the Scheffe Post-hoc Test showing the mean differences in groupings of Marital Status. It was noted that married freight forwarders had the highest measure on commitment to governmental policies that encourages trade facilitation (M=20.39, SD=1.76). This was followed by those that were divorced (M=19.91, SD=1.42), while the least was among those who were single (M=18.15, SD=3.41). The post hoc result indicated that the mean difference between married and single was significant (md=2.24, p < .05). Also, the mean difference between single and divorced was significant (md=1.76, p < .05). However every other mean

differences were not significant. This implied that the observed influence of marital status on commitment to governmental policies that encourages trade facilitation was attributed to the noted significant mean difference. Based on the outcome of the results, the formulated null hypothesis was rejected because it was not confirmed.

DISCUSSION

This study, as exploratory research, provided new insights into the confluence between workers' SES in the maritime sector and their willingness to comply with government

policies on trade facilitation. The first such insight is empirical evidence of a causal relationship between certain SES variables and the willingness to comply with governmental trade facilitation policies. While no previous studies that have provided such evidence, findings from various studies suggest a strong association between SES and attitudinal dispositions toward various issues, including operational performance. For example, Williamson (2007) and Ajayi and Mazinyo (2020) posited, based on empirical findings, that younger and less experienced truckers are most likely to engage in Substance Use Disorder (SUD) to reduce the stress associated with their work schedules. Also, Alcanlz et al. (2018) found that younger truckers, males, and unmarried individuals are more likely to engage in SUD. However, there is a dearth of studies that have considered the effects of different SES variables (gender, age, educational status, work experience, financial capability, and marital status) on compliance with trade facilitation (CTF) policies.

Based on this study's findings, literacy (as a component of SES) is a critical determinant of freight forwarders' willingness to CTF (Table 2). Earlier studies (Williamson, 2007; Jaing et al., 2017; Ajayi and Mazinyo, 2020) have affirmed a strong association between literacy level and Job Satisfaction Level (JSL) among truckers (a part of the transport sector workforce).

The study also highlighted the importance of a seemingly innocuous factor, such as workers' gender, and its role in CTF policies. The study found that male workers are more favourably disposed toward policies that encourage trade facilitation in the industry. On the surface, this discovery should reassure policymakers, given men's pole position in the industry. Statistics from this study revealed that 85.5% (335) of the respondents are male; it can therefore be inferred that the dominant

male population will drive future CTF policies. However, available statistics indicate a remarkable increase in the number of women employed in hitherto male-dominated job positions. Women in STEM Network (2025) reported that nearly 34% of females are 'breaking the glass ceilings in a male-dominated industry globally. Nwafor (2025) provided an insight into the Nigerian context, by showing that between 2019 and 2024, the number of female Chief Executive Officers (CEO) in the Nigerian banking industry increased astronomically from one to ten, which represents 36 percent of Nigerian major banks' CEOs, an indication of a paradigm shift in the gender-employment landscape in the country. While it may seem far-fetched to expect such a massive paradigm shift in the gender-employment structure of the freight forwarding industry in Nigeria, it could be a pointer to what is to be expected in the near future. Efforts must be made to unravel the reasons behind the tepid response of the female gender to CTF policies; such information is necessary to ensure the long-term sustainability of a support system for implementing governmental trade facilitation policies in the sector.

The study also revealed that freight forwarders' marital status is a significant factor influencing their attitudinal disposition towards their CTF policies (Table 3). Findings from studies that examined the confluence between workers' marital statuses and their commitment to the workplace's values indicated evidence of causality between them (Çemberci et al., 2022; Figueroa and Lemus, 2025). The findings from this study further reinforce this belief, indicating that married employees significantly influence CTF policies among freight forwarders. It can therefore be inferred that married employees are more likely to demonstrate higher organisational

commitment and performance towards CTF policies compared to their single, divorced, or widowed counterparts. Scholars generally attribute such increased commitment to the need for stability, better work-life balance, and support from a spouse.

Another reality unearthed by this research is that working experience or years of service among freight forwarders have no predictive power on the willingness to adopt CTF policies. Ordinarily, findings from previous studies suggest that organisational commitment to workplace policies is influenced by 'years of practice/work' among workers (Bai and Liu, 2018; Jia-Jun and Hua-Ming, 2022; Wojtczuk-Turek, 2025; Okon et al, 2025). It is generally assumed that a positive relationship exists between years of working experience (tenure) and employees' readiness to commit to the workplace's policies, as longer-tenured employees are often expected to exhibit higher affective and normative commitment due to increased investment in the organisations that employ them. The present finding counters this norm and calls for a deeper examination in future studies.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The principal aim of this study is to examine the confluence of key SES variables among freight forwarders (age, educational status, work experience, and marital status) and their effects on their willingness to adopt government-enacted CTF policies. The study recognised the importance of trade facilitation policies as a harbinger of economic development for the nation and also affirmed the indispensability of the freight forwarding industry in its catalysing role in achieving this. In conclusion, the results suggest that gender, age, educational qualifications, and marital status are important predictors of commitment

to governmental trade facilitation policies among freight forwarders. Policymakers and stakeholders in the freight forwarding industry should feel encouraged by these insights to develop targeted strategies that reflect current global realities, such as recruiting more qualified female professionals as freight forwarders, and periodic capacity development for staff to strengthen sector engagement.

AREAS OF FUTURE RESEARCH

Despite the relevance of the findings, this study has some limitations. The model derivation and subsequent statistical testing did not account for or adjust for the possibility of collinearity among some multivariate factors. There is a strong likelihood of collinearity among some of the SES variables. Finding from previous studies indicated the existence of collinearity between educational status, marital status, respondents' age and work conditions among workers in the transport industry, and their dispositions to issues relating to substance use disorder, willingness to enforce trade union rules, and obedience to operational safety standards (Jiang et al, 2017; Alcañiz, et al, 2018; Ajayi and Mazinyo, 2020; Lawal-Fagbo et al, 2023). Another possible limitation is making sweeping generalisations based on this study's findings, treating it as the 'proverbial silver bullet' to facilitate freight forwarders' commitment to trade facilitation policies in the country. The study excluded the role of infrastructure facilities and their determinants in achieving 'ease of doing business' and in improving the country's Logistics Performance Index (LPI) overall. Experience from other climes has shown that the availability of complementary infrastructure (power supply, intermodal linkages, and

communication services) triggers a measure of willingness among transport-sector workers to

comply with operational regulations (Matekenya and Ncwadi, 2022; Mohri et al., 2022).

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